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Mortality from Road Accidents in Europe

Between 2000 and 2020 it decreased on average of 66.70%

The indicator measures the number of victims caused by road accidents, including drivers and passengers of motor vehicles and pedal cycles, as well as pedestrians. People who die on road accidents up to 30 days after the accident occurred are counted as road accidents. After these 30 days, the reason for death could be declared differently. For the Member States that do not use this definition, corrective factors are applied. The average population of the reference year is used as a denominator-for 100,000 people.

Ranking of European countries by mortality value from road accidents in Europe in 2020. Romania is in the first place for mortality value from road accidents in 2020 with an amount of 8.5 units, followed by Latvia with an amount of 7.3 unit and from Bulgaria with a value of 6.7 units. Belgium is halfway through the value of mortality from road accidents in Europe with an amount of 4.3 units, followed by Luxembourg with an amount of 4.1 units and Italy with a value of 4 units. They close the Malta ranking with an amount of 2.1 units, followed by Sweden with a value of 2 units and Norway with 1.7 units.

Ranking of European countries by percentage decrease in mortality from road accidents between 2000 and 2020 in Europe. Iceland is in the first place due to decrease in the percentage of mortality from road accidents with a value equal to -80.70%, followed by Spain with a value of -79.58% and Norway with a value of -77.63 %. In the middle of the standings there are Belgium with a value equal to -69.93%, followed by Estonia with a value of -69.86% and Switzerland with an amount of -68.29%. The Netherlands closes the ranking with an amount of -55.88%, followed by Finland with an amount of -48.05% and Bulgaria with a value of -45.97%. On average, the value of road accidents between 2000 and 2020 decreased from 12.87 per 100,000 inhabitants to 4.28 per 100,000 inhabitants or a 66.70% reduction.

Clusterization with k-Means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is a clusterization with k-Means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. The identified Clusters are indicated below:

- Cluster 1: Italy, Slovakia, Belgium, Luxembourg, Austria, Slovenia, Estonia, Czech Republic, Portugal, Hungary, Cyprus, France, Spain;
- Cluster 2: Latvia, Lithuania;
- Cluster 3: Sweden, Switzerland, Norway, Netherlands, Denmark, Malta, Germany, Finland, Iceland, Ireland;
- Cluster 4: Poland, Croatia, Bulgaria, Romania, Greece.

From the point of view of the median, the following system of the Clusters or: $C2 = 6.75 > C4 = 6.6 > C1 = 4.3 > C3 = 2.7$ is the following system. From a strictly geographical point of view, it appears

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that the value of the median of the Baltic countries dominates the distribution, followed by the countries of Eastern Europe, and by southern Europe. Northern European countries have the lowest values of fatal road accidents.

Network analysis with the Euclidean distance. A Network Analysis is presented below with Euclidean distance. Two structures are identified with complex networks and three structures with simplified networks. There is the following network structure:

- The Netherlands have a connection with Switzerland for an amount of 0.93 units, and with Sweden for an amount of 0.5 units;
- Switzerland has a connection with the Netherlands for an amount of 0.93 units, with Sweden for an amount of 0.83 units and with Norway for an amount of 0.78 units;
- Norway has a connection with Switzerland for an amount of 0.78 units and with Sweden for an amount of 0.8 units;
- Sweden has a connection with the Netherlands for an amount of 0.5 units, with Switzerland for an amount of 0.83 units and with Norway for an amount of 0.8 units.

The following complex network structure is also detected:

- France has a connection with Austria for an amount of 0.81 units;
- Austria has a connection with France for an amount of 0.81 units and with Italy for an amount of 0.71 units;
- Italy has a connection with Austria for an amount of 0.71 units.

There are also simplified network structures or:

- Germany and Finland have a connection equal to an amount of 0.66 units;
- The Czech Republic and Bulgaria have a connection for an amount of 0.92 units;
- Croatia and Poland have a connection for an amount of 0.83 units.

Conclusions. Mortality from road accidents has decreased in all European countries between 2000 and 2020. However, there is a significant heterogeneity between the countries of the Baltic and Eastern Europe that have high mortality values for road accidents and the countries of the Northern Europe that have low mortality values from road accidents. It is likely that the improvement of motorway networks, cars technology, the experience of drivers, the spread of public transport and the culture of prevention have played a very significant role in reducing mortality from road accidents in Europe. A value that could further reduce itself in the presence of an intelligent motorway network which in connection with autonomous driving vehicles and equipped with artificial intelligence could allow a growth in road safety.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Rank	Country	2000	2020	Var Ass	Var Per	Rank	Country	2000	2020	Var Ass	Var Per
1	Iceland	11,4	2,2	-9,20	-80,70	16	Switzerland	8,2	2,6	-5,60	-68,29
2	Spain	14,2	2,9	-11,30	-79,58	17	Italy	12,4	4	-8,40	-67,74
3	Norway	7,6	1,7	-5,90	-77,63	18	Czechia	14,5	4,8	-9,70	-66,90
4	Luxembourg	17,4	4,1	-13,30	-76,44	19	Cyprus	16	5,4	-10,60	-66,25
5	Slovenia	15,8	3,8	-12,00	-75,95	20	Lithuania	18,3	6,2	-12,10	-66,12
6	Ireland	11	2,9	-8,10	-73,64	21	Germany	9,1	3,3	-5,80	-63,74
7	Latvia	26,8	7,3	-19,50	-72,76	22	Slovakia	11,7	4,5	-7,20	-61,54
8	France	13,3	3,7	-9,60	-72,18	23	Hungary	11,8	4,7	-7,10	-60,17
9	Denmark	9,3	2,7	-6,60	-70,97	24	Poland	16,5	6,6	-9,90	-60,00
10	Greece	18,9	5,5	-13,40	-70,90	25	Croatia	14,7	5,9	-8,80	-59,86
11	Portugal	17,8	5,2	-12,60	-70,79	26	Netherlands	6,8	3	-3,80	-55,88
12	Austria	12,2	3,6	-8,60	-70,49	27	Finland	7,7	4	-3,70	-48,05
13	Sweden	6,7	2	-4,70	-70,15	28	Bulgaria	12,4	6,7	-5,70	-45,97
14	Belgium	14,3	4,3	-10,00	-69,93	29	Malta	3,8	2,1	-1,70	-44,74
15	Estonia	14,6	4,4	-10,20	-69,86	30	Romania	11	8,5	-2,50	-22,73

Rank	Country	2020	Rank	Country	2020
1	Romania	8,5	16	Italy	4
2	Latvia	7,3	17	Finland	4
3	Bulgaria	6,7	18	Slovenia	3,8
4	Poland	6,6	19	France	3,7
5	Lithuania	6,2	20	Austria	3,6
6	Croatia	5,9	21	Germany	3,3
7	Greece	5,5	22	Netherlands	3
8	Cyprus	5,4	23	Ireland	2,9
9	Portugal	5,2	24	Spain	2,9
10	Czechia	4,8	25	Denmark	2,7
11	Hungary	4,7	26	Switzerland	2,6
12	Slovakia	4,5	27	Iceland	2,2
13	Estonia	4,4	28	Malta	2,1
14	Belgium	4,3	29	Sweden	2
15	Luxembourg	4,1	30	Norway	1,7

